

Time Dependent Density and Stochastic Approaches to Quantum Mechanics

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In the literature, stochastic approaches employed to derive the Schrodinger equation seem to focus on the idea of a classical spatial density which depends on time and space i.e. $\text{density}(x,t)$. As a result, d/dt (partial) density appears in various equations such as the continuity and Focker Planck equations. At one point in the derivation the quantum wavefunction is introduced “mathematically” as $W(x,t)=\sqrt{\text{density}(x,t)} \exp(i S(x,t))$ where S is related to a velocity field through $u(x,t)=\text{velocity} = d/dx S$. From quantum mechanics, $-Et$ becomes a term of S the velocity field. The stochastic/hydrodynamical approaches employ the term du/dt partial = d/dt (partial) $d/dx S$ and then “pull out” d/dx leaving d/dt (partial) S which yields $-E$ average energy from the $-Et$ term.

In this note we argue that for a bound quantum state $\text{density}(x)$ so d/dt (partial) density = 0, yet the statistical ideas of quantum mechanics should be present in such a case. Furthermore for the free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx-iEt)$, $\text{density}=1$. In fact, the Schrodinger equation should follow for a free particle even the case of $\text{density}=1$. Stochastic processes seem to be based on equations which consider a change in classical spatial density at a point x in time due to flow in or out or stochastic changes. Quantum processes seem to deal with periodic probability changes from one dimension to another $\exp(ipx)$ (2 dimensions) which are somehow related to a physical process of momentum flow. Ultimately one links this process to an energy conservation which does not seem to be the same as a classical stochastic/hydrodynamical approach.

In this note we argue that a free particle with a constant momentum p has periodic stochastic processes associated with it through its complex probability change in the region of its wavelength, but that these are linked to creating the momentum p . Furthermore momentum is linked to energy so we argue that the Schrodinger equation is a stochastic equation linking energy and momentum and that time and space are separated i.e. there is no situation of following a change in spatial density in time for a free particle with momentum p . For a bound state, one has a distribution of free particles, but again time is removed from the problem in the sense that it only appears in $\exp(-iEt)$ in the wavefunction to again establish a relationship between energy and average momentum and potential. There is again no nonzero d/dt (partial) density term which seems to be key in stochastic equations. Only if one takes a linear combination of energy eigenstates $\sum \text{over } E_n \text{ } a_n(E_n) \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ does one obtain the form $\text{density}(x,t)$, but we argue that quantum features should already appear in $\exp(ipx)$ and the bound state scenario with a zero d/dt (partial) $\text{density}(x,t)$. We argue, however, that the Schrodinger equation and fundamental stochastic ideas of quantum mechanics should already be present at the level of $\exp(ipx)$.

Stochastic Derivations of the Schrodinger Equation

There are numerous derivations of the Schrodinger equation in the literature; here we briefly mention two (1) (2). A main point seems to be the use of a classical spatial density which depends on time and space i.e. $\text{density}(x,t)$ and equations using d/dt (partial) density as well as

a velocity field which brings in E the average energy. The wavefunction is introduced as a mathematical convenience.

In (1), the continuity equation:

$d/dt (\text{partial}) \text{ density} = d/dx (\text{density } u)$ ((1)) where u is a velocity field defined by:

$u = 1/m d/dx S$ where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sqrt{\text{density}} \exp(i S/\hbar)$ ((2))

In principle following the approach of (1) one would not need to introduce a wavefunction at all, it is used to linearize an equation obtained using the continuity equation and a hydrodynamic force equation.

For a constant momentum p particle, equations (32) and (33) from (1) yield for $S = px - Et$

$0 = 0$ for (32) and $1/2m p^2 = E$ for ((33)) where $V(x) = 0$ i.e. energy conservation

For a bound state $S = -Et$ and equations from (1) yield:

$d \ln(\text{density}) / dt = 0$ for (32) which is already known because bound state density does not depend on time and for equation (35)

$E = V(x) - \hbar^2/2m (d/dx dW/dx)/W$ which is the time-independent Schrodinger equation if $\hbar = 1$ with $W(x)$ being the wavefunction.

Thus for both cases one obtains correct conservation of energy equations. It may be pointed out, however, that the hydrodynamical approach of (1) uses $u(x,t)$ as a velocity field and yet for both the bound and $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ cases:

$u(x,t) = \text{velocity field from hydrodynamics which is set equal to } dS(x,t)/dx$, but with

$S(x,t)$ containing a $-Et$ term. Thus when a $dS/dt (\text{partial})$ appears it yields E which is needed for energy conservation. The form $u = -dS/dx$ is introduced because $u(x,t)$ is irrotational so it is not clear why S, which is used to create a velocity field, should contain an Et term if the physical scenario is hydrodynamical flow. It seems rather that conservation of energy is really being introduced as we discuss in a further section.

It may be noted that $dS/dt (\text{partial})$ appears through:

$Du/dt = d/dt u (\text{partial}) + u du/dx$ (from equation (15) from (1)) ((4))

Given that $S = -Et + f(x)$ one should have: $d/dt u (\text{partial}) = 0$, yet a derivative d/dx is pulled out of the equation as a whole allowing $dS/dt (\text{partial})$ to remain and yield a term of average energy E.

An interesting result, however, is that the proper quantum mechanical form of average kinetic energy appears for a bound state in this formalism, namely $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx}$. This follows, however, from linking the stress tensor $s_{ij} = 1/m \langle [v_i - u_i][v_j - u_j] \rangle$ to $\ln(\text{density})$. In fact, the choice:

Kinetic energy = $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} \ln(\text{density})$ is used in (1) which is the quantum mechanical result, so the Schrodinger equation automatically follows.

In (2), d/dt (partial) density(x,t) is again present even though it is zero for both the bound and $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ cases. Furthermore, even though the approaches of (1) and (2) differ formally, both contain:

$[d/dt$ (partial) + $u_m \text{ dot grad}] u_m(x,t)$ in equation(25) of (2) which we call ((5)) in this note. This is identical to ((4)) above.

Again as in (1):

$u(x,t) = \text{velocity} = \hbar \text{ grad } \theta(x,t)$ where $W(x,t) = \text{wavefunction} = \sqrt{\text{density}} \exp(i \theta)$.

In other words, $\theta = S$ contains $-Et$ for both the quantum bound state and free particle. From ((5)) one sees that d/dt (partial) $u(x,t) = d/dt$ (partial) $d/dx \theta$. The d/dx term may ultimately be "pulled out" leaving d/dt (partial) $\theta = -E$. As a result, the velocity field $u(x,t)$'s change in time is supplying the average energy term which seems unusual. Furthermore, d/dt (partial) $d/dx (-Et)$ is zero, but by removing d/dx , the term stands.

As a result, we consider the emergence of the Schrodinger equation for the bound state or $\exp(ipx)$ cases from a stochastic approach to possibly be unusual as $-Et$ is part of $\theta(x,t)$ which is used to define a velocity field $d/dx \theta(x,t)$. Instead we argue that one should be able to derive the Schrodinger equation for a free quantum particle with constant momentum and that quantum fluctuations and the idea of time and space should appear at this level.

Independent Change of x and t in the Classical Action

In the last section we argued that although stochastic approaches to quantum mechanics have the mathematical form of hydrodynamical type equations with a velocity flow, at least two cases (bound states and $\exp(ipx)$) do not have a time dependent density and the velocity flow is used to bring in a term of E (average energy) which seems to belong to a conservation of energy type equation and not linear velocity.

In a previous note (3) we argued that one may vary x and t independently in both the nonrelativistic and relativistic free particle classical actions to obtain:

$$d\text{Action}/dt = -E \text{ and } d\text{Action}/dx = p \quad ((5))$$

As a result, one may consider t and x independent so matters are not the same as deterministic classical mechanics. From ((5)) one may create a conservation of energy equation which also

has the appearance of a kind of continuity equation although with $i \frac{d}{dt}$ (partial) and not $\frac{d}{dt}$ in addition to constants and a special definition for velocity. One does not, however, necessarily need to think in terms of the continuity equation. For the nonrelativistic case, ((5)) leads to:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} W = -\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W \quad \text{where } W = \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((6))$$

((6)) represents a free particle with Action = $ipx - iEt$. Thus one has the Schrodinger equation already at the level of free particle by having x and t independent which describes some kind of stochastic process. Time in this case appears as a place holder for energy, but also indicates a kind of cycling in time related to a resonance. This becomes clearer in the bound state case which also has a factor $\exp(-iEt)$ in the wavefunction representing the resonance energy. This is completely removed from the free particle momentum distribution $W(x) = \sum \text{over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Again a conservation of energy equation is used in the bound state case:

$$[\sum \text{over } p \quad p^2/2m \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)] / [\sum \text{over } p \quad a(p) \exp(ipx)] + V(x) = E \quad ((7))$$

((7)) is equivalent to the Schrodinger equation.

One may note that in the free particle case $\exp(ipx)$ has two dimensions and a modulus of 1. density(x,t) in classical stochastic processes counts particle number in a volume and so is linked to the modulus of the wavefunction. The two dimensional probability of $\exp(ipx)$ may be linked perhaps to one dimension being along the particle motion and the other in a perpendicular plane. In such a case there is an internal spatial density associated with a single particle (but stochastic classical processes would not discern such internal density). They are only interested in particle count in a small volume. ((6)) seems to indicate that the very motion of a quantum particle is associated with both a conservation of energy equation and a periodic probability shift from one dimension to another ($\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$). There is a spatial change of probability in each dimension in time [$\cos(px - Et) + i \sin(px - Et)$] even though the overall probability (1 particle) does not change. As a result ideas related to changing probability densities are present, but with the result of establishing conservation of energy. The Schrodinger equation seems to be more of a conservation of energy equation at least for bound states and $\exp(ipx)$ than an equation focusing on changing particle spatial density due to velocity flows. Nevertheless the idea of probability flows from one dimension are present due to what we argue is a physical process associated with momentum flow i.e $\exp(ipx)$. This scenario, however, does not seem to be identical to classical hydrodynamical physics although there appear to be strong similarities.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that although a number of stochastic/hydrodynamical approaches utilized to derive the Schrodinger equation exist in the literature, these seem to focus on a spatial density which counts particle number and changes in time due to velocity flow. For a quantum system, bound states and $\exp(ipx)$ [a free particle with constant momentum] do not have a spatial density which changes in time. Furthermore the two theories considered in this note (1)(2) bring average energy into the definition of $u(x,t)$ the velocity flow which we argue is

unusual. A function $S(x,t)$ is introduced such that $u(x,t)=d/dx S(x,t)$ and $S(x,t)$ contains $-Et$ as a term. Equations are developed which contain $du/dt \text{ partial} = d/dt \text{ partial} d/dx S$ and d/dx is "pulled out" leaving $d/dt \text{ partial} S$ which yields $-E$ for the $-Et$ term of S . For $-Et$, $d/dt(\text{partial}) d/dx (-Et)=0$ yet energy emerges.

We argue in this note that a conservation of energy approach seems to be the main driver and it should apply already at the level of $\exp(ipx)$ a free particle with constant momentum. We note that if one varies t and x independently in the classical action then $d\text{Action}/dt=-E$ and $d\text{Action}/dx = p$ from which one may create directly a conservation of energy equation which is the Schrodinger equation in the nonrelativistic case and the Klein-Gordon equation in the relativistic. $\exp(ipx)$ shows that there is complex probability or a probability in two dimensions, but its modulus is 1 showing that particle number is conserved. The density used in classical stochastic processes is only related to particle number and does not capture internal probability shifts within a particle i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. We argue that probability shift $\cos(px) + i \sin(px)$ represents a physical process associated with energy transport (i.e. momentum) and that the Schrodinger equation links energy and energy flow (conservation of energy) together with this periodic shifting probability which is reminiscent of hydrodynamics, but not identical.

References

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